

EUROPEAN MIDDLEWARE INITIATIVE

EMI TORQUE SERVER CONFIG

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EMI CREAM TORQUE server config

Functional Description

The CREAM Torque server config is a metapackage that consists of

- the configuration module, yaim-torque-server
- dependencies on the TORQUE batch system (server side) and MAUI scheduler

System Administrator Documentation:

- If installing and configuring the TORQUE server in the same node as the CREAM Computing Element follow the CREAM documentation:
 - ◆ CREAM installation of the batch system
 - ◆ CREAM Configuration
- If installing and configuring the TORQUE server on a separate node, follow the instructions present in the Generic Installation & Configuration for EMI 1:
 - ◆ TORQUE Server Installation&Configuration

-- DoinaCristinaAiftimiei - 08-May-2011

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